

D7.3: Communication and dissemination plan

[WP7 – Communication and dissemination]

Lead contributor	Josepine Fernow, Uppsala University
	josepine.fernnow@crb.uu.se
Other contributors	Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead, Trilateral Research
	Philip Brey, Philip Jansen, University of Twente
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Abstract

This document includes strategies and action plans for scientific dissemination, internal and external communications for the SIENNA project. A tentative list of audiences, objectives and key messages for internal and external communications and an initial action plan for 2017-2018 is included. It outlines a three-step approach to external communications, where tactics in the initial phase (month 1-12) focus on raising awareness of the existence of the project, identifying and connecting with stakeholders. In the second phase (month 12-30), tactics will move from raising awareness to active collaboration with key stakeholders to develop strategy for impact collaboration, involving stakeholders in shaping key messages. Networks, projects and initiatives identified in the first year will be assessed for potential collaborations that could support the dissemination of outputs from, and impact of, the SIENNA project. The third phase of SIENNA communications (month 31-42) will build on the knowledge produced in the first and second phases. The strategies, activities, tools and tactics outlined in this document build on a SWOT analysis for external communications.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V0.1	30 Oct 2017	First Draft		Authors
V0.2	28 Nov 2017	Second draft		Authors
V0.3	4 Dec 2017	Version for Quality Assurance and review	Review	QA reviewers, all consortium members
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V1.1	18 October 2018	Updated version	Adding Annex 6, Guidelines for SIENNA dissemination and communications review	Authors

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
D7.3 Communication and dissemination plan	Action plans for communication and dissemination activities are included in this document.
T7.2 Website launch and maintenance	Procedures for maintaining and updating the SIENNA project website are outlined in this document.
T7.3 Graphical identity and guidelines for use	Graphical identity and procedures to develop guidelines for use are part of this document.
T7.4 Scientific dissemination	Procedures for creating and maintaining the scientific dissemination plan are outlined in this document.
T7.5 Stakeholder communication and public relations	Tools and tactics for stakeholder communication and public relations are outlined in this document.
T7.6 Measuring outreach	Procedures for tracking are described in this document.
T1.4 Conduct stakeholder analysis and compile a contact list	The tools and tactics described in this report will feed into the stakeholder analysis and the associated D1.2 deliverable.

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Executive Summary

The SIENNA project will use a three-step approach to external communications, where tactics in the *initial phase* (month 1-12) focus on raising awareness of the existence of the project, identifying and connecting with stakeholders. In the *second phase* (month 12-30), tactics will move from raising awareness to active collaboration with key stakeholders to develop strategy for impact collaborations, involving stakeholders in shaping key messages for their peers. Networks, projects and initiatives identified in the first year will be assessed for potential collaborations that could support the dissemination of outputs from, and impact of, the SIENNA project. The *third phase* of SIENNA communications (month 31-42) will build on the knowledge produced in the first and second phases and focus on executing already developed plans.

This document shows how effective communications and dissemination strategy will:

- enable SIENNA consortium members to effectively communicate and meet overall objectives;
- effectively engage with, and tailor communication and dissemination to, stakeholder groups, and ensure our stakeholders understand the value of SIENNA results;
- enable SIENNA to disseminate and communicate the results of the project in a timely manner;
- enhance the project's visibility and reputation and foster its impact widely, at the EU and international level;
- change stakeholder behaviour and perceptions where necessary;
- demonstrate the success of the SIENNA project;
- set measurable goals and objectives of communication and dissemination.

The document describes strategies for how to both exploit strengths and opportunities, and mitigate the risks posed by weaknesses and threats to SIENNA communications. Tools and tactics builds on a SWOT analysis for SIENNA communication (Annex 2). The document outlines a tentative list of audiences, objectives and key messages for SIENNA communications. It includes a list of SIENNA owned channels (e.g. SIENNA website, social media and future e-newsletters), channels available to us through partners or consortium members (e.g. official press-releases, partner social media) and actions for how and when these channels can and should be used to communicate key messages to various audiences.

This strategy is translated to the operational level in *action plans* that list concrete communication activities and timelines for the implementation of the communication strategy. The activities planned will facilitate timely and consistent presentation of the project and its results to stakeholders and other audiences. This plan defines with *whom* (the audience), *why*, *when*, *what* (the type of activity), *where* (the channel) communication is expected and *who* is responsible for implementation of the activities.

This plan is a living document and will be revised regularly to meet the needs of SIENNA in the second and third phases as outlined above.

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EMP	Ethical Monitoring Protocol
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PMC	Project Management Committee
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
URL	Address on World Wide Web
WP	Work Package

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Alt-text	Alternative text for images (i.e. word or phrase inserted as an attribute in in the code (HTML) of a web page. This text can be read by text-to-speech functions, and, when images cannot be displayed, alt-text will appear in place of the image.
Audience	Group for which SIENNA communication or dissemination is targeted.
Communication objective	Goals for SIENNA communication that can be used to identify audiences develop messaging strategies and evaluate the effectiveness of SIENNA communications.
Consortium	Collectively, all parties that have signed the Consortium Agreement.
Consortium member	Individual involved in the SIENNA project.
Content owner	Individual responsible for accuracy of content in specified channel (or part of channel)
Dissemination	Active and tailored scientific (or research) communication of results to different academic audiences.
External communication	Adapting and informing about key messages and/or disseminations for different audiences.
Impact collaboration	Process to co-create and amplify local impact. For the purposes of this report, the term is used to describe an approach engaging stakeholder audiences, developing key-messages together, and activating and leveraging existing networks and channels owned by audiences.
InfoGlue	Content Management System (CMS) used by Uppsala University.
Internal communication	Sharing information between partners and/or members within the SIENNA consortium
Key message	The main points SIENNA wants target audiences to hear and remember.
Landing page	Main point of entry (start page) for general and/or specific audiences on the SIENNA website.
Partners	All partners of the SIENNA project – full or associate. ‘Full partners’ refers to any of the 11 beneficiaries of the project who receive funding for project activities. ¹ ‘Associate partners’ refers to the two non-crucial partners who do not receive funding for project activity.

¹ SIENNA, Description of Action, Part B, p. 38.

Term	Explanation
Plain language	Communicating in a clear, concise and structured way, avoiding jargon or convoluted language (aka plain writing or plain English).
Readability testing	Using algorithms developed to test the level of education/literacy required to comprehend text with specific attributes and/or structure (e.g. number of words in sentences, length of words).
Stakeholder	A relevant actor (persons, groups or organisations) who: (1) might be affected by the project; (2) have the potential to implement the project's results and findings; (3) have a stated interest in the project fields; and, (4) have the knowledge and expertise to propose strategies and solutions in the fields of genomics, human enhancement and human machine interactions i.e., artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. (SIENNA D1.2 definition)
Visual identity	Graphical identity and other visual components (such as colour scheme, fonts) used in SIENNA communications (i.e. web, printed materials, report and presentation templates).

Table 2: Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

Communication and dissemination require input from all partners and is the responsibility of the entire SIENNA consortium. This means that facilitating efficient *internal communications* is a pre-requisite for effective *external communications*. This document outlines the direction of SIENNA project communication and dissemination, including priorities, target groups, messages, tools, tactics and resources for communication. In addition, it outlines the organisation of both internal and external communications.

Promoting the achievements of the project, the benefits and the necessity of involvement is crucial to ensure experts and stakeholders become and remain engaged, ensuring the impact of SIENNA outputs is sustained after the project ends. The document establishes guidance and processes for communication and dissemination in the SIENNA project, intended to drive communication and dissemination throughout the lifecycle of the SIENNA project. This plan is a living document, and it will be updated regularly as needs progress along with the project.

The document describes strategies for how to both exploit strengths and opportunities, and mitigate the risks posed by weaknesses and threats to SIENNA. These tools and tactics builds on a SWOT analysis for SIENNA communication (Annex 2). The document outlines a tentative list of audiences, objectives and key messages for SIENNA communications. This strategy is translated to the operational level in *action plans* that list concrete communication activities and timelines for the implementation of the communication strategy.

1.1 Statement of purpose

This document shows how effective communications and dissemination strategy will:

- enable SIENNA consortium members to effectively communicate and meet overall objectives;
- effectively engage with, and tailor communication and dissemination to, stakeholder groups, and ensure our stakeholders understand the value of SIENNA results;
- enable SIENNA to disseminate and communicate the results of the project in a timely manner;
- enhance the project's visibility and reputation and foster its impact widely, at the EU and international level;

- change stakeholder behaviour and perceptions where necessary;
- demonstrate the success of the SIENNA project;
- set measurable goals and objectives of communication and dissemination;
- ensure SIENNA communications adhere to H2020 communication guidelines.

The activities planned will facilitate timely and consistent presentation of the project and its results to stakeholders and other audiences. This plan defines with *whom* (the audience), *why*, *when*, *what* (the type of activity), *where* (the channel) communication is expected and *who* is responsible for implementation of the activities.

1.2 Guiding principles

SIENNA communications should be as accurate as possible, avoiding exaggerated statements in the areas of genetics and genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interaction (i.e., AI and robotics). Communication should be relevant to the SIENNA project and the audiences defined in this plan. Furthermore, communications coming out of this project should be accessible and inclusive. As SIENNA has a diverse set of audiences, experts in one of the areas covered by SIENNA might be unfamiliar with the other areas. This requires striking a balance between writing for a mixed target audience, while remaining interesting to experts.

The SIENNA dissemination and communication strategy is guided by the following basic principles:

Principle	Definition
Factual	Communication should be accurate and adapted to the target audience.
Transparent	Communication should be transparent, regarding contributions, authorship, data management and any conflicts of interest.
Consistent	SIENNA should offer tools that enable partners to communicate in a consistent manner. Both in terms of visual identity and other forms of messaging.
Respect	Communications (both internal and external) are a core part of the SIENNA project's culture and should be based on respect for our audiences, partners and members of the consortium.

2. Governance

The procedures for SIENNA communications are outlined below. These procedures have been put in place to ensure communication inside and outside the SIENNA consortium are carried out in a timely and consistent manner. This document outlines strategy and plan three separate tasks: project internal communication (coordinated by WP8, University of Twente), external communication (coordinated by WP7, Uppsala University) and scientific dissemination (coordinated by WP7, Trilateral Research).

Activity	Responsible person(s)	
Decisions on general communication and dissemination policy	PMC	
Approval of ad hoc messages	Coordinator, if unavailable, then decisions are taken by the deputy coordinator	
Approval of ad hoc communications	WP7 leader	
Review and approval of manuscripts for scientific publications	Will be outlined in Annex 6: Guidelines for SIENNA disseminations and communications	
Spokespersons to media and journalists	For SIENNA general	Coordinator, deputy coordinator
	For published results	Authors

Activity	Responsible person(s)
Coordinating communication efforts with H2020 project and policy officers	Coordinator
Tracking and storing consent to publish photo and/or video identifying an individual (on SIENNA SharePoint server and locally at Uppsala University)	WP7 leader
Gold open access	Governance decision will be taken spring 2018

Table 3: Governance structure for SIENNA communications

3. Scientific dissemination strategy

The **aim of SIENNA's scientific dissemination strategy** is to share findings and results with the ethics and scientific community and ensure the longevity of project results via publications and participation in third-party events (see list of potential events in Annex 5). We aim to publish our results in high impact English language journals (a non-exhaustive list is outlined in Annex 5). SIENNA adheres to the principle of open science. To ensure those who do not have access to or cannot afford journal subscriptions, SIENNA has an open access publication policy, providing green open access standard, some key publications will be gold open access. Participation in events will also help communicate SIENNA's work and findings, networking with various type of stakeholders. The consortium partners will present views, share findings, results, and network.

SIENNA envisages webinars as part of its stakeholder and public engagement policy and plans to carry out six webinars with 50 stakeholders as part of the tasks pertaining to the work packages specific to the three technologies (WPs 2-4) and Task 6.5: reconcile needs of researchers and the legitimate concerns of citizens. The WP leaders will discuss and finalise topics for the webinars in consultation with the PMC and/or the WP7 lead. Webinars will be held online and will be publicised widely via the SIENNA website and Twitter account to recruit participants.

Gold open access strategy and requirements for what constitutes a key publication will be discussed and decided by the PMC in spring 2018. Planning of webinars will be carried out by WP2, 3, 4 and 6 leaders with support from the WP7 communications team.

3.1 Audiences for scientific dissemination

Our scientific dissemination strategy aims to reach a variety of audiences using both publication and event participation means, e.g., academics, researchers, scientists, policy-makers, ethicists and professionals, innovators, and civil society. This will ensure SIENNA results have a wide and long-lasting impact. The table below presents a preliminary indication of the key performance indicators (KPIs) linked to the scientific dissemination activity – these will be reviewed as the project progresses.

Activity	KPI
Scientific publications	5 publications submitted/accepted (by month 42)
Open access	Gold open access or green open access provided by end of journal embargo
Webinars	6 webinars held by month 42
Presentations at third-party events (conferences and workshops)	9 held by month 42

Table 4: Key performance indicators for scientific dissemination

4. Internal communication

The **aim of SIENNA's internal communications** is to foster collaboration within the SIENNA project, ensuring consortium members are informed about project activities, how to contribute to them and play their role in the project.

Clear structures for internal communications foster transparent and efficient interaction, sharing of results and information and helps create and maintain a project identity. Internal communication is the responsibility of the WP8 management team, who have set up and will maintain a repository for project information (SIENNA SharePoint), manage key documents and contact lists. WP7 will also support internal communications by providing tools for consortium members to communicate about the project. A clear strategy for internal communications will be developed in Q1 2018, including, for example, review guidelines for scientific publication, development of processes for review and quality assurance of deliverable reports and publications.

Audience	Internal communications objective (ICO)	Internal Communications Key messages (ICM)
SIENNA consortium members	<p>ICO 1: Enable and encourage transparent and efficient interaction</p> <p>ICO 2: Share results and information in an efficient manner</p> <p>ICO 3: Create and maintain a project identity</p> <p>ICO 4: Provide tools to help SIENNA consortium members communicate about the project</p> <p>ICO 5: Provide tools to educate and familiarise consortium members on content, activities and results relating to the SIENNA project</p> <p>ICO 6: Share information about what is happening in the broader scientific and academic world with and between SIENNA consortium members</p> <p>ICO 7: Evaluate the effectiveness of SIENNA communications throughout the duration of the project</p>	<p>ICM 1: Know what has been discussed in the Programme Management Committee (PMC)</p> <p>ICM 2: Know that they are listened to and that their advice is considered</p> <p>ICM 3: Know how their advice has been used</p> <p>ICM 4: Know where to find basic information</p> <p>ICM 5: Know the progress and relevance of SIENNA</p> <p>ICM 6: Feel involved, informed, motivated, accountable and respected</p> <p>ICM 7: Actively disseminate information about SIENNA to their organisations and/or networks</p>
SIENNA partner organisations	ICO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	ICM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7

Audience	Internal communications objective (ICO)	Internal Communications Key messages (ICM)
		ICM 8: Create content about SIENNA for their communication channels
SIENNA scientific advisory board members	ICO 1, 2	ICM 5, 6, 7 ICM 9: Maintain interest in the project ICM 10: Actively collaborate by reviewing SIENNA deliverables and participating in workshops
SIENNA H2020 project and policy officers	ICO 8: Support communications between SIENNA, the H2020 programme and other relevant projects and initiatives	ICM 2, 3, 4, 5

Table 5: Tentative audiences, objectives and key messages for internal communications

5. External communication

The **aim of SIENNA's external communications** is to 1) create awareness of the project, its scope and results within stakeholder communities, 2) create a sense of ownership and willingness to implement SIENNA results by different stakeholders (including research ethics committees, professional organisations and policy-makers) for genetics and genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interaction (i.e., AI and Robotics).

Consistent messaging and a clear project identity helps ensure SIENNA is identifiable and recognisable as an entity. A tentative list of audiences and communication objectives have been developed for the initial phase (month 1-12). The list will be developed further for the second phase of SIENNA communications (month 12-30) based on the *SIENNA D1.2 Stakeholder analysis and contact list* report coming out of WP1 in month 7.

In preparation for the final phase of communicating the SIENNA project (month 31-42), key messages will be developed together with stakeholders using a model for impact collaboration. Strategy for each phase is described under section 6 (Tools and tactics) below. This includes developing strategy for identifying and reaching underserved audiences.

Audience	External Communications Objective (ECO)	External Communications Key Message (ECM)
Field experts in genetics and genomics	ECO 1: Generate and maintain interest in the SIENNA project and its outputs ECO 2: Inform about the goals, benefits and/or progress of SIENNA ECO 3: Establish connections with external audiences	ECM 1: Be aware of SIENNA, its goals, progress and importance ECM 2: Know that SIENNA will develop ethical frameworks for research ethics protocols and professional ethics codes

Audience	External Communications Objective (ECO)	External Communications Key Message (ECM)
	<p>ECO 4: Engage external audiences to help shape SIENNA proposals</p> <p>ECO 5: Influence external audiences to adopt and implement SIENNA proposals</p> <p>ECO 6: Disseminate results from SIENNA</p> <p>ECO 7: Be clear about what is within the scope of SIENNA</p> <p>ECO 8: Place SIENNA in the broader world of RRI and ELSI research on new and emerging technologies</p>	<p>ECM 3: Know that SIENNA will develop proposals for better regulation</p> <p>ECM 4: Know that SIENNA is open to collaboration</p> <p>ECM 5: Know that stakeholder and expert input is valued and taken into account</p> <p>ECM 6: Know that experts, stakeholders and members of national publics gave input to the project</p> <p>ECM 7: Expect proposals and outputs from the SIENNA project</p> <p>ECM 8: Share findings that interest them</p> <p>ECM 9: Become aware of the ethical and human rights issues related to SIENNA technology areas</p> <p>ECM 10: Know SIENNA approaches to methodological issues</p> <p>ECM 11: Develop willingness and ability to implement SIENNA proposals</p>
Field experts in human enhancement	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Field experts in human-machine interaction, specifically AI and robotics	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Field experts in ethics and law	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Research ethics committees and councils (regional and national), associations of REC's	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Research funding agencies (regional and national)	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, 11

Audience	External Communications Objective (ECO)	External Communications Key Message (ECM)
Professional organisations	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Related projects and networks	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 ECO 9: Share learnings about the effectiveness of communications from SIENNA	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10
Policy makers (regional and national)	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 9, 11
Civil Society Organisations (CSO'S)	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	ECM 1, 2, 6, 7, 11
Industry	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	ECM 1, 2, 6, 7, 11
The public and society at large	ECO 2, 4, 6	ECM 6, 9

Table 6: Tentative audiences, objectives and key messages for external communications

6. Tools and tactics

SIENNA covers a wide range of topics, with diverse target audiences. For this reason, SIENNA channels and tools need to be adaptable to fit different tactics for different audiences. The SIENNA website uses four separate landing pages to accommodate for tailoring communications to audiences interested in either the SIENNA approach in general, or only one of the three technology domains covered by SIENNA. Tailoring will also be required for other channels described in section 7, for which graphical elements and/or versions of the SIENNA logo will be developed.

Routines to evaluate news value and tactics for public deliverable reports and publications will be set up by WP7 and WP8 to ensure that 1) deliverable reports submitted for quality assurance review and 2) manuscripts distributed for IP review, are shared with the WP7 communications team in order to plan and prepare different communication activities.

6.1 Approach to developing tactics for SIENNA communications

The strategy to communicate about the SIENNA project and its results will be developed using a three-step approach, dividing the project into three phases. This report is focused on tools and tactics for the first phase of the project, suggesting a skeleton for phase two and three.

In the **initial phase** (month 1-12) of the SIENNA project, tactics focus on raising awareness of the existence of the project, identifying and connecting with stakeholders. SIENNA will also develop tools to help ensure audiences receive information tailored to their interests. Tools and tactics for this phase includes:

- domain-specific landing pages on SIENNA website;
- creation of graphical elements and/or tailored logo versions for each domain;
- development of video and text content for different domains;
- tailoring social media strategy for different domains;

- development of strategy to tailor newsletters to different audiences;
- allowing stakeholders to specify area(s) of interest when connecting with SIENNA;
- categorising area(s) of interest in stakeholder analysis and contact list;
- identification of similar initiatives and areas of overlap;
- describing and communicating the scope of the SIENNA project clearly;
- developing examples to describe problems addressed by the project to lay audiences;
- development of tailored strategy to support SIENNA impact in different areas;
- development of strategy for cross-disciplinary and cross-professional communication of SIENNA publications to ensure relevant results reach relevant domains;
- building networks outside the SIENNA consortium to extend our reach;
- development of anchoring strategies and framing for each technology area to support public understanding of the scientific and technological domains covered by SIENNA;
- avoiding sensationalist framing.

In the **second phase** of SIENNA communications (month 12-30), tactics will move from raising awareness to active collaboration with key stakeholders to develop strategy for impact collaboration. Stakeholders will be involved in shaping key messages for their peers. Networks, projects and initiatives identified in the first year will be assessed for potential collaborations that could support the dissemination of outputs from, and impact of, the SIENNA project. This includes:

- development of strategy for impact collaboration together with stakeholders;
- development of key messages for SIENNA communications together with stakeholders;
- development of working collaborations with similar projects, networks and initiatives to leverage networks and support SIENNA impact;
- differentiate SIENNA messages from similar and/or overlapping initiatives to avoid competition;
- sharing learnings from SIENNA communications with similar projects and initiatives;
- development of strategy and plan to translate summary versions of SIENNA outputs to other languages;
- development of strategy for communicating SIENNA proposals.

The **third phase** of SIENNA communications (month 31-42) will build on the knowledge produced in the first and second phases and focus on executing already developed plans. This phase involves:

- development of initial strategy for sustainability of SIENNA communications;
- sharing learnings from SIENNA communications to ensure sustainability of impact support after the project ends.

6.2 General tactics for communicating about SIENNA

The diverse range of audiences for SIENNA communications means we need to acknowledge that most of our audiences lack expertise in some of the areas covered by SIENNA. For this reason, tactics for communicating complex messages to non-expert audiences need to be put in place. This includes ensuring external communications are interesting and inclusive to all audiences, that British English spelling is used in SIENNA's official channels to reflect that SIENNA is a European-funded project, that content is readable and adapted to the audience. This includes:

- developing and enforcing SIENNA visual identity;
- using gender neutral and inclusive language;
- selecting images that represent different genders, ethnicities and (dis)abilities;
- encouraging partners to translate SIENNA communication materials to local languages;
- using readability testing tools and standards to increase comprehension and SEO;

- using plain language as a starting point when communicating with lay audiences;
- developing templates to help SIENNA consortium members adhere to the SIENNA visual identity and accessibility standards;
- considering colour contrast and the use of alt-text for images on the web;
- using text and subtitling in video to enable silent viewing;
- developing glossaries of terms to ensure SIENNA communicates in a concerted fashion;
- using partners logos in SIENNA communications to benefit from established trademarks and showcase our geographical spread;
- using consortium member's portrait photos and biographies in SIENNA communications to showcase the competence within, and multi-disciplinary nature of, the project.

We aim for available and accessible communications. This means that accessibility and availability considerations have priority before the visual communication in all SIENNA channels. It includes simple measures such as ensuring Word templates have proper tags for headings to enable automatic generation of tables of content that allow text-to-speech functions to navigate documents. It also includes testing and offering tools on the SIENNA website and ensuring it follows accessibility standards in line with Uppsala University policy. Further tools and tactics for the SIENNA website are outlined in the *SIENNA D7.2 Website launch* report.

Note on text in SIENNA communications: To measure text-readability of English language text produced for official SIENNA communication channels, we use Flesh-Kincaid and/or SMOG readability formulas. Both measure readability in terms of number of years of schooling required to understand a text. For SIENNA official communications, we aim for a grade average of 14 and routinely test text using online readability scoring tools. However, when producing materials specifically aimed at lay audiences, we aim for a score between 8 and 12, depending on the complexity of the content.

Note on images in SIENNA communications: Part of the communication involves presenting the people involved in the project, publishing pictures and video of them on the SIENNA website and other channels and media. For this reason, all consortium members are asked to sign a consent form (described in *D8.2 Ethical monitoring protocol*). We will also review licences before using stock photography to ensure we have permission to publish.

7. Channels and multipliers

The SIENNA project has a number of official channels maintained by the WP7 team at Uppsala University (mainly website and social media). Through our partners, we have access to an additional number of channels that can be used to communicate or multiply SIENNA messages:

Channel	Description	Use and timing	Channel owner
Website	The main contact point for the project	Launched in connection with project start (October 2017)	SIENNA official, maintained by Uppsala University
Opinion editorials	Editorial text in scientific journals, professional societies, daily press, depending on purpose	As needed, for example to:	Authors
		Define project scope	Authors
		Inform about key publication/results	Author partners
		Inform about recommendations	Authors

Channel	Description	Use and timing	Channel owner
SIENNA events	Events open to stakeholders and experts e.g., SIENNA workshops and the final event.	Throughout the project lifecycle	Host partner
Presentations at third-party events	Presentations at external meetings, conferences and workshops related to genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interactions.	Throughout the project to raise awareness and present SIENNA findings and results	Consortium partners
Press releases and other public relations activities	Press releases and/or press briefings aimed for global release* or selected journalists	Launch	University of Twente
		Key publications/results	First author partner
		SIENNA events	Host partner
		Publications with news value	First author partner
		Project ends	University of Twente
Newsletters (external)	Periodical electronic communication to defined subscribers	First issue after SIENNA starts generating results	SIENNA official, maintained by Uppsala University
Social media	YouTube channel for video developed for SIENNA and other web	As and when needed	SIENNA official, maintained by Uppsala University
	Twitter	Strategy to be developed based on stakeholder analysis in WP1	SIENNA official, maintained by Uppsala University

Table 7: List of channels and multipliers for SIENNA messages

***Note:** These communications can be drafted and coordinated by SIENNA, but are always *distributed through a partner press-office* who owns the channel used for this occasion.

Strategy for (and coordination of) opinion editorials and presentations at third party events will be developed in the *first phase* of SIENNA communications.

7.1 SIENNA website

The SIENNA website was launched in October 2017. This is the main point-of-contact and the website is structured to allow tailoring communications to specific audiences. The *SIENNA D7.2 Website launch* report describes the structure of the SIENNA website, the visual identity of the project, and the process used to develop content for the SIENNA website. It describes the website's role in SIENNA communications, serving as the main point of contact for the project, with a structure that allows the consortium to tailor communications for different target audiences as the project progresses. It also describes the first steps towards developing a communications and dissemination strategy for SIENNA. Procedures for website maintenance are outlined in Annex 3.

Figure 1: SIENNA website landing pages and tailored content

7.2 SIENNA newsletters

The SIENNA project will issue regular electronic newsletters (quarterly) distributed on lists maintained on the Sympa list server at Uppsala University. Electronic newsletters will re-use content developed for the SIENNA website and social media. Subscribers are encouraged to sign up on the SIENNA website. Recipients will also be identified based on the stakeholder analysis (WP1, D1.2) and asked to opt in should they want to receive regular SIENNA communications.

Audiences, objectives and key messages for SIENNA newsletters follow those identified in section 5 *External audiences*. Like the website and other SIENNA communications, communicating effectively through electronic newsletters likely also requires tailoring to different audiences. This strategy will be developed during 2018.

Action	Format	Status
Discussion need for SIENNA internal newsletter	Meeting	Proposed
Discussion on strategy and audiences for SIENNA external newsletter(s)	Meeting	Planned
Creation of e-mail lists	Sympa list server at UU	Planned
Issue of first newsletter(s)	Communication by Month 12 (October 2018)	Planned

Table 8: Tentative timeline for planning issuing of SIENNA e-newsletters

7.3 Public relations: sharing SIENNA results with a wider audience

WP7 will help partners assess the news value of publications and events, draft press releases and opinion editorial text in collaboration with first author and/or host partners. WP7 will coordinate

activities and liaise with relevant partner press-offices, who have local knowledge and access to channels for global press releases (see section 7 *Channels and multipliers*). WP7 will develop contacts with (a limited number of) journalists, science bloggers and media outlets. However, the main strategy for press communication is liaison with partner press-offices to leverage local knowledge and existing relationships.

WP7 will evaluate news value and plan communications of SIENNA results during the regular IP review procedures for publications put in place in the Consortium Agreement. SIENNA will mirror SIENNA related press releases, web news and opinion editorials on our website and social media. Partners will be encouraged to multiply messages via their communication platforms, connections and networks.

WP7 will provide basic media training and provide advice to consortium members. WP7 will also put routines in place for how to track and evaluate the sentiment of SIENNA related publications, and guidelines for how to handle negative publicity.

7.4 Participation in scientific and public debate

SIENNA consortium members will participate in both scientific and public debate to support impact and uptake of SIENNA outputs. Strategy will be developed for the second phase of SIENNA communications (month 12-30).

7.5 Participation in third party events

SIENNA participation in third party events will aid the dissemination of information about the project and its results, and build support for the consortium's proposed ethical frameworks and codes of conduct.

SIENNA consortium members will present and discuss findings with researchers, scientists and innovators and contribute to the scientific, industry and policy debates and discussions. Strategy for presentations of results at third party events will be developed for the second phase of SIENNA communications (month 12-30).

7.6 SIENNA social media

Many of the topics covered by SIENNA are already discussed on online and social media platforms. To ensure SIENNA is part of this discussion, and help extend the reach of SIENNA communications, we will use a combination of official SIENNA social media channels and channels owned by partners and stakeholders in the project. An initial social media strategy was developed for the project launch, using the #SiennaEthics hashtag, a twitter account (@SiennaEthics) and a SIENNA YouTube² channel for project video.

A comprehensive social media strategy for SIENNA will be developed in spring 2018. This strategy will consider elements included in the generation of Altmetric data to ensure strategies for social and other online media generate outputs that can be tracked, measured and presented in a way that allows for benchmarking and other forms of comparison.

7.6.1 YouTube

The SIENNA project will use videos to communicate with a number of audiences. A SIENNA YouTube channel was launched on November 1, 2017. The first video produced for the SIENNA YouTube channel was produced for the European Union's DG Research and Innovation (RTD) R&I project playlist.

² SIENNA on YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSn_2EYn7tDgz7ZD3fcF_0w

The YouTube channel plays an important role communicating about SIENNA to the RTD team and other European research projects. The RTD team have begun building a portfolio of project videos showcasing the impact of EU funded research in the daily lives of Europeans. This means there is an incentive for using YouTube to share project videos. The advantages are many: YouTube videos can be embedded on websites using iframes, shared in social media, it is possible to subscribe to YouTube channels and link individual videos, search terms can be added and viewings are tracked.

Figure 2: SIENNA YouTube channel

7.6.2 Twitter

SIENNA launched an official twitter channel on November 6, 2017. The initial strategy is to follow organisations, stakeholders and experts identified in the stakeholder analysis carried out by WP1 (task 1.4). This includes individuals and organisations active in ethics, bioethics, law and the three technology domains, coupled with media outlets and influencers who could potentially disseminate SIENNA messages.

In the initial phases, SIENNA partners' institutional accounts and consortium members active on twitter are instrumental to building a following. The @SiennaEthics account follows partners and individuals. Consortium members are asked to follow us back, and help share information their networks by re-tweeting content from the account.

In the initial phases, content relating to the project launch on partner websites and other media outlets will be shared on a regular basis (weekly) to showcase the international and multi-disciplinary nature of the project. Project videos and website content will also be shared, followed by deliverables and publications from the project. In the advent of publications and outputs from the SIENNA project, we will re-tweet partner's publications relevant to SIENNA. Twitter will also be used to direct traffic to content on the SIENNA website.

Figure 3: SiennaEthics on twitter (www.twitter.com/siennaethics)

8. Measuring SIENNA outreach

Uppsala University is responsible for setting up monitoring systems and Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) for project communication and dissemination. Communication activities will be tracked and reported in an interim report (D7.4) and a final report (D7.5) on project communication.

Activity	Tool	Responsible
Website traffic	Google Analytics	Uppsala University
Social media coverage of scientific publications	Altmetric	Uppsala University
Scientific publications	Tracking of manuscript review/DiVA portal	Trilateral Research/Uppsala University
Green open access download	DiVA portal	Uppsala University
Citations	Web of Science	Uppsala University
Press coverage	Manual tracking/Google alerts	Uppsala University/Partner press offices
Participation in third party events	Manual tracking/survey	Uppsala University

Table 9: Proposed monitoring systems for tracking SIENNA communications and dissemination

9. Action plans

Note: The action plans below outline planned and completed communication activities per December 2017. This is an initial plan for the first phase of SEINNA communications. Activities have not been planned to meet all objectives and key messages for all audiences.

Objectives and key messages for internal communications

Objectives for internal communications (ICO)	Key messages for internal communications (ICM)
<p>ICO 1: Enable and encourage transparent and efficient interaction</p> <p>ICO 2: Share results and information in an efficient manner</p> <p>ICO 3: Create and maintain a project identity</p> <p>ICO 4: Provide tools to help SIENNA consortium members communicate about the project</p> <p>ICO 5: Provide tools to educate and familiarise consortium members on content, activities and results relating to the SIENNA project</p> <p>ICO 6: Share information about what is happening in the broader scientific and academic world with and between SIENNA consortium members</p> <p>ICO 7: Evaluate the effectiveness of SIENNA communications throughout the duration of the project</p> <p>ICO 8: Support communication between SIENNA, the H2020 programme and other relevant projects and initiatives</p>	<p>ICM 1: Know what has been discussed in the Programme Management Committee (PMC)</p> <p>ICM 2: Know that they are listened to and that their advice is considered</p> <p>ICM 3: Know how their advice has been used</p> <p>ICM 4: Know where to find basic information</p> <p>ICM 5: Know the progress and relevance of SIENNA</p> <p>ICM 6: Feel involved, informed, motivated, accountable and respected</p> <p>ICM 7: Actively disseminate information about SIENNA to their organisations and/or networks</p> <p>ICM 8: Create content about SIENNA for their communication channels</p> <p>ICM 9: Maintain interest in the project</p> <p>ICM 10: Actively collaborate by reviewing SIENNA deliverables and participating in workshops</p>

Internal communication action plan 2017-2018

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
All audiences (SIENNA consortium members, partners, members of Scientific Advisory Boards, H2020 project and policy officers)									
Periodic	Inform about completion of milestones and deliverables	Milestone and deliverable reports	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	ICM 1, 4, 5, 6, 7	Task leads, Philip Brey		Ongoing
October 2017	Inform about completion of D7.1 press release	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 3, 4	ICM 7	Josepine Fernow, Philip Brey		Completed
December 2017	Inform about completion of D7.2, website launch	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2, 3, 4, 5	ICM 4, 6, 7	Josepine Fernow, Philip Brey		Almost completed
December 2017	Informing about completion of D7.3 Communication and dissemination plan	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2, 3, 4, 5	ICM 4, 6, 7	Josepine Fernow	Philip Brey	On time

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q2 2018	Informing about completion of D2.1 State –of-the-art-review of human genomics	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2, 6	ICM 4, 5, 9	Heidi Howard	Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec, Philip Brey	Planned
Q2 2018	Informing about completion of D3.1 State –of-the-art-review of human enhancement	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2, 6	ICM 4, 5, 9	Saskia Nagel	Sean Jensen, Philip Brey	Planned
Q2 2018	Informing about completion of D4.1 State –of-the-art-review of human-machine interactions	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2, 6	ICM 4, 5, 9	Philip Brey	Rowena Rodrigues, Philip Jansen	Planned
Q4 2018	Informing about D1.1 the consortiums' methodological handbook	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2	ICM 4, 5, 9	Rowena Rodrigues	Stearns Broadhead, Philip Brey	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q4 2018	Informing about D1.2 stakeholder analysis and contact list	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2	CM 4, 5, 9	Rowena Rodrigues	Stearns Broadhead	Planned
Q4 2018	Informing about survey of REC approaches and codes for human genomics	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2	ICM 4, 5, 9	Heidi Howard	Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec, Philip Brey	Planned
Q4 2018	Informing about survey of REC approaches and codes for human enhancement	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2	ICM 4, 5, 9	Saskia Nagel	Sean Jensen, Philip Brey	Planned
Q4 2018	Informing about survey of REC approaches and codes for human machine interactions	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2	ICM 4, 5, 9	Philip Brey	Rowena Rodrigues, Philip Jansen	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
October 2018	Informing about completion of D8.1 first project interim report	Deliverable report	Submission to H2020, SharePoint server	E-mail, SIENNA website	ICO 2	ICM 4, 5, 9	Philip Brey	Rowena Rodrigues, Philip Jansen	Planned
Audience: SIENNA consortium members									
Periodic	Facilitate planning and scheduling work, co-ordination with and between all partners, ensuring the integration between work packages and fulfilment of the project's objectives.	Project management committee (PMC) meetings	E-meetings	SharePoint, e-mail lists	ICO 1, 2, 3, 4	ICM 4, 5, 6, 7	Philip Brey	Carola Bouwens	Ongoing
August 2017	Information sharing within the consortium	E-mail lists	SharePoint server		ICO 1, 2, 4, 5	ICM 1, 4, 6, 9	Carola Bouwens	Philip Jansen	Completed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
September 2017	Provision of tools: PowerPoint template	Template	SharePoint server	E-mail lists	ICO 3	ICM 7, 8	Josepine Fernow		Completed
October 2017	Information sharing within the consortium	Kick-off	Face2Face meeting		ICO 1, 2, 3, 6	ICM 1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 10	Philip Brey	Carola Bouwens	Completed
October 2017	Information sharing within the consortium	Deliverable report 7.1 Press release	Deliverable report on SharePoint server		ICO 1, 2, 3, 4	ICM 5, 6, 7, 8	Josepine Fernow		Completed
December 2017	Provision of tools: Deliverable report template	Word template	SharePoint server	E-mail lists	ICO 3, 4	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Rowena Rodrigues	Under development
Q1 2018	Review guidelines for scientific publication	Document	SharePoint server	E-mail	ICO 3, 4	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Rowena Rodrigues, Anna Holm	Planned
Q1 2018	Development of process for ensuring	Meeting	Minutes		ICO 1, 2	ICO 4	Josepine Fernow	Rowena Rodrigues	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
	publications submitted or review are shared with the WP7 communications team for planning purposes								
Q1 2018	Development of process for ensuring that deliverable reports submitted for QA are shared with the WP7 communications team for planning purposes	Meeting	Minutes		ICO 1, 2	ICO 4	Josepine Fernow	Rowena Rodrigues	Planned
Q1 2018	Discussion on internal communication strategy	Meeting	Minutes	E-mail, SharePoint	ICO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ICM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10	Philip Jansen	Philip Brey, Carola Bouwens, Sean Jensen, Rowena Rodrigues,	Proposed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
	(newsletter, e-mail lists)							Josepine Fernow	
Q1 2018	Survey consortium members plans to disseminate SIENNA results (input for scientific dissemination plan)	Survey	Online survey (e-mail)		ICO 1, 2, 5	ICM 7, 8	Rowena Rodrigues	Stearns Broadhead	Planned
Q1 2018	Development of guidelines for SIENNA disseminations and communications	Annex to communication and dissemination plan	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 1, 2, 4	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead	Planned
Q1 2018	Development of process for developing and maintaining communication and scientific dissemination plan	Annex to communication and dissemination plan	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 1, 2	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead, Philip Jansen	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q1 2018	Decision on repository for tracking SIENNA publications and green open access	Meeting with decision by PMC to confirm use of UU DiVA portal repository	E-mail	SIENNA website	ICO 1, 2	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	PMC members	Planned
Q1 2018	Routines for tracking SIENNA publicity	Document	SharePoint		ICO 1, 2, 7	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q2 2018	Development of process for evaluation of SIENNA impact and influence	Annex to communication and dissemination plan	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 7	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q2 2018	Planning for first SIENNA newsletter	Meeting	Minutes		ICO 2, 3, 4, 8	ICM 7, 8, 9	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q2 2018	Provision of tools: Report template	Word template	SharePoint server	E-mail lists	ICO 4	ICM 4	Anna Holm	Josepine Fernow	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q2 2018	Provision of tools: high resolution logo	Logo (eps)	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 4, 8	ICM 4, 7, 8	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q2 2018	Provision of tools: Widescreen PowerPoint template	PowerPoint template	SharePoint server	E-mail lists	ICO 4	ICM 4	Anna Holm	Josepine Fernow	Planned
Q3 2018	Information about deliverable D9.1 (ethics) H – Requirement No.1 (confidential)	Deliverable report	SharePoint Server	E-mail lists	ICO 2	ICM 4	Philip Brey	Philip Jansen	Planned
Q3 2018	Information about deliverable D9.2 (ethics) POPD - Requirement No.2 (confidential)	Deliverable report	SharePoint Server	E-mail lists	ICO 2	ICM 4	Philip Brey	Philip Jansen	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q3 2018	Provision of tools: logos and/or graphical elements per technology domain	Image (jpg, eps)	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 4, 8	ICM 4, 7, 8	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Philip Jansen	Proposed
Q3 2018	Provision of routines for accessing stakeholder list	Document	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 1, 2	ICM 4	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Stearns Broadhead	Planned
Q3 2018	Development of guidelines for how to handle negative press	Guideline/procedure	SharePoint	E-mail lists	ICO 1, 3, 4	ICM 4, 6, 8	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q3 2018	Media training for SIENNA consortium members	Training	Webinar, document	SharePoint, E-mail lists	ICO 1, 3, 4	ICM 4, 6, 8	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q3 2018	Survey consortium members plans to disseminate SIENNA results (input for	Survey	Online survey (e-mail)		ICO 1, 2, 5	ICM 7, 8	Rowena Rodrigues	Stearns Broadhead	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
	scientific dissemination plan)								
October 2018	Information sharing within the consortium	SIENNA annual consortium meeting	Face2Face meeting		ICO 1, 2, 3, 6	ICM 1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 10	Philip Brey	Carola Bouwens, Philip Janssen	Planned
Audience: Scientific advisory board members									
Q4 2017	Invitation to first SIENNA workshop in Uppsala (May 2018)	Invitation	E-mail		ICO 1, 2	ICM 5, 6, 9	Heidi Howard	Josepine Fernow	Planned
Audience: SIENNA H2020 project and policy officers									
Periodic	Submission of deliverable reports	Report	H2020 participant portal	E-mail	ICO 2,8	ICM 5	Philip Brey		Ongoing
November 2017	Invitation to first SIENNA workshop in	Invitation	E-mail		ICO 1, 2	ICM 5, 6	Philip Brey		Complete

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
	Uppsala (May 2018)								
October 2017	Periodic report	Report	H2020 portal	E-mail	ICO 1, 2	ICM 5, 6	Philip Brey		Planned

Table 10: Action plan for internal communications

Objectives and key messages for external communications

Objectives for external communications (ECO)	Key messages for external communications (ECM)
ECO 1: Generate and maintain interest in the SIENNA project and its outputs	ECM 1: Be aware of SIENNA, its goals, progress and importance
ECO 2: Inform about the goals, benefits and/or progress of SIENNA	ECM 2: Know that SIENNA will develop ethical frameworks for research ethics protocols and professional ethics codes
ECO 3: Establish connections with external audiences	ECM 3: Know that SIENNA will develop proposals for better regulation
ECO 4: Engage external audiences to help shape SIENNA proposals	ECM 4: Know that SIENNA is open to collaboration
ECO 5: Influence external audiences to adopt and implement SIENNA proposals	ECM 5: Know that stakeholder and expert input is valued and taken into account
ECO 6: Disseminate results from SIENNA	ECM 6: Know that experts, stakeholders and members of national publics gave input to the project
ECO 7: Be clear about what is within the scope of SIENNA	ECM 7: Expect proposals and outputs from the SIENNA project
ECO 8: Place SIENNA in the broader world of RRI and ELSI research on new and emerging technologies	ECM 8: Share findings that interest them
ECO 9: Share learnings about the effectiveness of communications from SIENNA	ECM 9: Become aware of the ethical and human rights issues related to SIENNA technology areas
	ECM 10: Know SIENNA approaches to methodological issues
	ECM 11: Develop willingness and ability to implement SIENNA proposals

External communication action plan 2017-2018

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
All audiences									
Periodic	Updates to website	News items, links, updated content	Website	Social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 1, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Ongoing
Periodic	Social media updates	Sharing content from SIENNA and/or partners	twitter, YouTube	Partner social media, SIENNA website feeds	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 1, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Ongoing
October 2017	Inform all audiences about SIENNA	Website	Website	Links from partner websites	ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow		Completed
October 2017	Inform all audiences about SIENNA	Press release	EurekAlert	SIENNA website, partner websites, press release from University of Granada,	ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow	Laurens van der Velde	Completed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
				Ethics Blog, SIENNA Twitter, partner social media channels					
October 2017	Presenting SIENNA to participants at Brave New World conference, Netherlands	Flyer (print)	Brave New World conference, 2-3 November 2017, Leiden, NL https://braveneworld.nl/	SharePoint accessible for SIENNA partners for other purposes.	ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow	Philip Brey, Philip Janssen, Sean Jensen	Completed
October 2017	Inform all audiences about SIENNA	Social media hashtag #SiennaEthics	twitter #SiennaEthics	Partner Twitter channels	ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow		Completed
October 2017	Establish social media presence	Launch of SIENNA YouTube channel	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSn_2EYn7tDgz7ZD3fcF_0w		ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow		Completed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
October 2017	Inform all audiences about SIENNA	Video presenting the SIENNA project: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0qb1A-mwnYU	SIENNA YouTube channel	SIENNA website, partner websites, partner twitter channels, SIENNA twitter channel	ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow		Completed
November 2017	Establish social media presence	Launch of twitter channel	twitter @SiennaEthics	Partner Twitter channels	ECO 1	ECM 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9	Josepine Fernow		Completed
Q1 2018	Incorporation of GDPR privacy notice and consent on all forms used to collect personal data on the SIENNA website	Addition of text and mandatory checkboxes	SIENNA website		ECO 3	ECM 4	Josepine Fernow	Stearns Broadhead	Planned
Q1 2018	Website structure review: adding section to	Web page	SIENNA social media	Partner social media	ECO 6	ECM 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
	showcase deliverable reports								
Q1 2018	Production of video content about ethical issues in human genetics and genomics	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Heidi Howard, Anna Holm	Planned
Q1 2018	Production of video content about ethical issues in human enhancement	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Saskia Nagel, Anna Holm	Planned
Q1 2018	Production of video content about ethical issues in AI & Robotics	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Philip Brey, Anna Holm	Planned

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q2 2018	Development of social media strategy for SIENNA	Meeting	Document for inclusion in D7.3		ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Planned
Q3 2018	Production of video content about social issues in human genetics and genomics	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Heidi Howard, Anna Holm	Proposed
Q3 2018	Production of video content about social issues in human enhancement	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Saskia Nagel, Anna Holm	Proposed
Q3 2018	Production of video content about social issues in AI & Robotics	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Philip Brey, Anna Holm	Proposed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q3 2018	Production of video content about social issues in human genetics and genomics	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Santa Slokenberga, Anna Holm	Proposed
Q4 2018	Production of video content about legal issues in human enhancement	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Saskia Nagel, Zuzanna Warso, Anna Holm	Proposed
Q4 2018	Production of video content about legal issues in AI & Robotics	Video	YouTube	SIENNA website & twitter, partner social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Philip Brey, Zuzanna Warso, Anna Holm	Proposed
Q3 2018	First SIENNA newsletter issued	E-mail newsletter	E-mail list	SIENNA website, partner websites, SIENNA	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm	Proposed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
				social media					
Q4 2018	Develop strategy for impact collaboration and key messages for key stakeholders	Meeting	Report	E-mail	ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Rowena Rodrigues, Philip Brey, Heidi Howard, Saskia Nagel	Proposed
Q4 2018	Discussion of strategy to reach underserved audiences	Meeting	Minutes		ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Philip Brey, Rowena Rodrigues	Proposed
Q4 2018	Discussion of strategy for SIENNA consortium members' participation in scientific and public debate	Meeting	Minutes		ECO 1, 2, 3, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8, 10, 11	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Philip Brey, Rowena Rodrigues	Proposed

Timing	Communication intent	Communication format	Communication channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Q4 2018	Discussion on strategy for SIENNA presentations at third party events	Meeting	Minutes		ICO 2	ICM 7	Josepine Fernow	Anna Holm, Philip Brey, Rowena Rodrigues	Proposed

Table 11: Action plan for external communications

Scientific dissemination plan 2018

Timing	Dissemination intent	Dissemination format	Dissemination channel	Multipliers	Objective	Key message	Lead	Other contributors	Status
Internal audience: SIENNA consortium members, Scientific advisory boards									
Periodic (Q1 & Q3)	Populating scientific dissemination plan	Update	Document	PMC meeting, SharePoint	ICO 1, ECO 6	ICM 6	Rowena Rodrigues	Stearns Broadhead	Planned
Q1 2018	Discussion and decision on Gold Open Access strategy and criteria for key publications	Meeting	Minutes	E-mail, SharePoint	ICO 1, 2, 3, 4	ICM 1, 4, 8	Philip Brey	Rowena Rodrigues	Planned
Audience: Field experts									
November 2-3 2017	Presenting SIENNA to stakeholders	Keynote presentation	Brave New World conference on how future technology will impact human life https://www.b	Interview with Philip Brey on DutchNews.nl SIENNA web news, SIENNA twitter	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11	Philip Brey		Completed

			ravennewworld.nl/						
April 2018	Presenting and discussing SIENNA results with stakeholders, experts and professional organisations	Fundamentals workshop	Meeting	Milestone report	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Heidi Howard	Rowena Rodrigues Philip Brey, Zuzanna Warso, Dirk Lanzerath	Planned
Q3 2018	Sharing more detailed information about findings and recommendations with stakeholders in genetics and genomics	Webinar with 50 participants	GoToMeeting	SIENNA website, SIENNA social media, partner websites & social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Heidi Howard	Santa Slokenberga, Emilia Niemiec, Alexandra Soulier, Josepine Fernow, Anna Holm	Proposed
Q3 2018	Sharing more detailed information about findings and recommendations with stakeholders in	Webinar with 50 participants	GoToMeeting	SIENNA website, SIENNA social media, partner websites & social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Saskia Nagel	Sean Jensen, Josepine Fernow, Anna Holm	Proposed

	human enhancement								
Q3 2018	Sharing more detailed information about findings and recommendations with stakeholders in AI & Robotics	Webinar with 50 participants	GoToMeeting	SIENNA website, SIENNA social media, partner websites & social media	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Philip Brey	Philip Janssen, Josepine Fernow, Anna Holm	Proposed
November 2018	Presenting and discussing SIENNA results with European lawmakers	Legal analysis workshop	Meeting	Milestone report	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Zuzanna Warso		Planned
Q4 2018	Share results from WP2	Scientific publication	Manuscript	SIENNA website, SIENNA social media, partner websites & social media (if news value, press-release from first author partner press office)	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Heidi Howard		Proposed

Q4 2018	Share results from WP3	Scientific publication	Manuscript	SIENNA website, SIENNA social media, partner websites & social media (if news value, press-release from first author partner press office)	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Saskia Nagel		Proposed
Q4 2018	Share results from WP4	Scientific publication	Manuscript	SIENNA website, SIENNA social media, partner websites & social media (if news value, press-release from first author partner press office)	ECO 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8	ECM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	Philip Brey	Rowena Rodrigues	Proposed

Table 12: Action plan for scientific dissemination

Annex 1: SIENNA visual identity

An initial visual identity for the SIENNA project was developed for the launch of www.sienna-project.eu (outlined in the *SIENNA D7.2 Website launch* report). The aim is to make SIENNA:

- Visible as an entity
- Identifiable in the European project context
- Uniform in external and internal communications

The visual identity will be used in all SIENNA communication materials, including PowerPoint templates and deliverable reports. Other templates will be developed by WP7 in the initial phase of the project (and defined in the Communication and Dissemination Plan). The visual identity is outlined below.

Tools	Guidelines	Background/motivation
Colour scheme	<p>Orange HEX# FF7F00 CMYK 0/50/100/0, PMS 2018C</p> <p>Purple HEX# 46008C CMYK 50/100/0/45 PMS 2091C</p> <p>Black</p> <p>Grey</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contrast for screen • Colours are neutral and not connected to specific technology area or scientific field (compare blue = medicine, red = danger).
Logo	<p>Font: Agency FB, regular Orange & black “landscape” format Adaptable</p>	<p>Plain:</p>
Web design	<p>Builds on Uppsala University's template for non-UU websites. Orange (#FF7F00) Purple (#46008C) Black Grey</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contrasting colours • Tested for accessibility • Contemporary look • Easy to re-create in print

PowerPoint template	White background, Black text, grey and green.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mirrors web-design • Accessible to colour blind people.
Fonts	PowerPoint: Arial Web: Arial Report headings: Arial Report body: Calibri	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available • Readable
Other print materials	To be finalised	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posters, booklets and flyers will mirror the SIENNA PowerPoint template and web design.

Table 13: SIENNA visual identity

The SIENNA project uses graphics that are in the public domain, mainly from www.pixabay.com. As a rule, we will not use images that are watermarked (with or without © marking) in digital communication. For portrait photos given to us by members of the consortium in SIENNA communications, we assume that the consortium member has the right to share it with us. When available, we include the photographer’s names in metadata of the image. In cases where a photo is clearly taken by a professional photographer, our policy is to ask whether we are free to use the image before using it in digital or printed media. Examples of images (in the public domain) below:

Annex 2: SIENNA SWOT analysis

A short SWOT workshop session was held at the SIENNA kick-off meeting on October 20, 2017, with the aim to inform the strategies for internal and external communications. The work done by partners consisted of a post-it brainstorming session facilitated by Josepine Fernow, WP 7 lead, who summarised input from partners, grouped it into categories and suggested strategy to mitigate weaknesses and threats, and use strengths and opportunities to SIENNA's advantage.

Tables below consist of notes from post-its (left column), grouped and categorised using a simplified systematic text condensation approach (middle column). Strategies form the basis for the tools and tactics described in the body of this document.

Weaknesses

List of weaknesses internal to the SIENNA consortium that could impede either internal or external communications, risk posed, and ways to mitigate them.

Type of weakness (as described in brainstorming session)	Risk (category)	Mitigation strategy
Challenges to internal communications		
Different language	Language and communication problems within the consortium	Develop strategy for internal communications
Miscommunication among partners		
Size of consortium		
Culture differences: within this project might exist different understanding of some concepts	Challenges because of diversity within the consortium	Address in WP1 work and consortium handbook
Coordination costs	Limited budget	Clarity about budget and strategy for SIENNA meetings
Expensive to travel long distances		
Challenge striking a balance between partners with more experience and money versus those with less	Different levels of influence	Strategy for ensuring everyone's voice is heard in the Project Management Committee
Bureaucratic process for approving press releases	Procedural/structural challenges	Develop clear internal review procedures
Deadlines could affect quality		
Too many cooks		
Too many emails make it difficult to sift important things from less important things that don't require attention		
Difficult to strike a balance between what major partners know and decide & keeping minor partners engaged and interested (& not switch off" or overload them)		
"Blame" comments are not helpful (e.g. "we don't want free riders, people sitting on their bum doing nothing") are not helpful		
		Ensure proper planning of communication activities
		Consider developing an internal newsletter or communication strategy for diminish information overload
		Work to ensure a positive project culture develops

Type of weakness (as described in brainstorming session)	Risk (category)	Mitigation strategy
Challenges to external communication		
Difficult technical issues	Difficult to communicate about SIENNA topics	Develop strategy to present SIENNA in different ways to different audiences: 1) the SIENNA approach, 2) SIENNA genomics, 3) SIENNA Human Enhancement and 4) SIENNA AI & Robotics
Too much speculation		
Diverse topics that might not have too much in common		
A lack of clarity about what some topics include		
Irrelevant/too abstract in light of more pressing problems		
Diversity in networks, languages and expertise	Diversity within the consortium in terms of the different geographical regions communications needs to cover	Develop strategy to involve and use partners expertise and networks
Differences between regions/country		
Few or no journalists in the consortium	Competences missing	Actively build networks in regions where partners are less well connected Liaise with partner's press offices
Most partners are academic. This might hinder communications with non-academic stakeholders	Academic style	Provide editorial support and review for external communications to support adaptation of messages to audience and channel

Table 14: Weaknesses internal to the consortium, risks posed, and strategy to mitigate them

Strengths

List of strengths internal to the SIENNA consortium that can support external communications, associated benefits and exploitation strategies.

Type of strength (as described in brainstorming session)	Benefit (category)	Exploitation strategy
Different languages	Adapting and translating SIENNA messages	Encourage partners to make communications available in local languages
Language pluralism		
Were from many countries	Networks and local knowledge	Use partner networks and channels
Geographic spread		
International		
Having partners outside Europe		
International partners		
Multinational team		
Presence in multiple countries		
Several partners outside of EU	Diverse expertise and backgrounds within the consortium	Use consortium expertise to develop tailored
Interdisciplinary in consortium		
Broad range of expertise generally		

Type of strength (as described in brainstorming session)	Benefit (category)	Exploitation strategy
Diverse consortium Real communications expertise Multidisciplinary Diverse expertise of participants People with different backgrounds		communications for SIENNA audiences
Expert led with public engagement It benefits for some organisations as hospitals, industry etc., for ethical codes, and decision-making	SIENNA approach Relevance	Ensure to include the strengths of the SIENNA approach and relevance of topics in messaging strategy
JOS [WP7 leader] Having a comms partner Dedicated comms plan Time to develop comms plan	Resources and time allocated for communications	Use a step-wise approach to develop strategy and plan for SIENNA communications to ensure work is fit for purpose

Table 15: Strengths internal to the consortium, associated benefits, and exploitation strategy

Opportunities

Opportunities external to the SIENNA consortium that can help communications from the project, associated benefits and exploitation strategies.

Opportunities (as described in brainstorming session)	Benefit (category)	Exploitation strategy
Topics already in the public domain Popular topics Relevant topics Topics relevance High tech interest >> relevance/interest in topic	There is already an interest in SIENNA topics	Consider framing SIENNA topics to fit current (public, academic and professional) debate(s)
European Commission channels	Using H2020	Use existing H2020 channels to showcase SIENNA in the EU research context
Liaison with other projects Other projects	Collaborations	Identify, connect and collaborate with other projects and initiatives to support SIENNA impact
Scientific expertise and expert channels, for example EAHL for Health Law Kantar's network and communication channels	Existing networks and communications channels	Develop strategy to access and use third party channels for SIENNA communications

Partner networks		
Strong prior affiliations of members		
Festivals, symposia etc. about the technologies	Participating in third party events	Identify venues and develop strategy to create space for SIENNA communication and dissemination in stakeholder arenas
Events: NGO's		
Events: Industry		
Events: Academia		
Events: Public		
Events: Policy makers		

Table 16: Opportunities external to the consortium, associated benefits, and exploitation strategy

Threats

List of threats to SIENNA communication (external to the consortium), risk posed and suggested mitigations.

Threats (as described in brainstorming session)	Risk (category)	Mitigation strategy
Conservative audiences for "sensitive issues"	Public perceptions	Avoid sensationalist framing, use consistent messaging
Public knowledge of technologies limited	Difficult to communicate the complexity of ethical and legal dilemmas relating to technology that is difficult to understand	Develop anchoring strategies and framing for each technology area to support public understanding of science Media training for SIENNA consortium members Provide editorial support and review for external communications to support adaptation of messages to audience and channel
Difficult to communicate complicated content		
High tech subjects: need to simplify leads to wrong information		
Popular science channels & language		
Oversimplified treatment of these issues in media		
Oversimplified treatment of the technologies in the media		
Excessive coverage of topics – competition	Competition	Identify similar initiatives, connect and develop strategy to either 1) collaborate to support impact, 2) differentiate message to avoid confusion

Table 17: Threats external to the consortium, risks posed, and strategy to mitigate them

Annex 3: Governance, review and maintenance of SIENNA website

All pages on the SIENNA website have assigned **content owners**. Owners are responsible for reviewing the accuracy of the content and approve updates. The WP7 leader is the **chief editor** of the website. Members of the WP7 team at Uppsala University carry out updates.

Content owners (outlined in table 18) are responsible for the accuracy of website content. They are also responsible for initiating updates when major changes occur in the project, such as changing roles within the consortium, publication of results, when milestones and deliverables are met.

Page	Content owner
www.sienna-project.eu	Josepine Fernow
/about-sienna/	Philip Brey
/about-sienna/structure/	Philip Brey
/about-sienna/theory-and-methodology/	Rowena Rodrigues
/about-sienna/eia/	Philip Janssen
/about-sienna/stakeholders/	Rowena Rodrigues
/about-sienna/proposals/	Dirk Lanzerath
/about-sienna/genralize/	Zuzanna Warso
/about-sienna/contact/	Josepine Fernow
/genomics/	Heidi C. Howard
/human-enhancement	Saskia Nagel
/AI and robotics/	Philip Brey
/news/	Josepine Fernow
/partners/	Philip Brey
/partners/people/	Carola Bouwens

Table 18: Content owners www.sienna-project.eu

The SIENNA WP7 leader will take a proactive role, initiating review and updates in relation to periodic reports to H2020 and when information is requested for inclusion in newsletters and other communications.

Event triggering website content update & review	Scheduling	Responsibility
Periodic reports	Annual	WP7 leader
Newsletter request for content contribution	Periodic	WP7 leader
Scientific publication	Upon publication.	Author/WP7
SIENNA workshop	Pre-and post-event	Organiser
Press release or other press activity	Upon publication	WP7 leader
News item contribution from consortium member	Upon delivery	Author
Suggestion from consortium member	Ad hoc	Individual
PMC decisions	Ad hoc	WP7 leader
Production of communication materials	Upon production.	WP7 leader
Work package progress	Ad hoc	WP leaders

Table 19: Events triggering content update and review of www.sienna-project.eu

The website structure is described in the *SIENNA D7.2 Website launch* report. However, as the project develops, the website structure will likely require oversight. Events that could trigger the need for a structure review are outlined below:

Event triggering website structure review	Time	Lead
First publication (adding section to list publications)	Ad hoc	WP7 leader
First workshop (advertising)	Spring 2018	WP7 leader
First external newsletter	Not later than October 2018	WP7 leader
Periodic reports	Annual	WP7 leader
Publication of first submitted deliverable reports	Ad hoc	WP8 leader

Table 20: Events triggering structure review of www.sienna-project.eu

Annex 4: Process for developing and maintaining communication and scientific dissemination plans

Scientific dissemination plan

Task lead: Rowena Rodrigues, Trilateral Research

Two annual surveys (Q1 and Q3) will be sent to all consortium members to solicit information about where they intend to submit abstracts for presentations, publication plans, and to which deliverables those publications relate.

Surveys are used to populate the scientific dissemination action plan. The action plan will be tracked by the WP7 communications team, both against requests to review manuscripts, individual follow-up and general requests for information at regular PMC meetings. The PMC will discuss publication plans in relation to deliverable reports to ensure the publication of deliverable reports on the SIENNA website does not interfere with plans for scholarly publications.

Internal communications

Task lead: Philip Brey, University of Twente

Initiating work to develop and update action plans for internal communications are a joint responsibility of WP8 and WP7 leads. The internal communication plan will be reviewed and approved by members of the PMC.

External communications

Task lead: Josepine Fernow, Uppsala University

Initiating work to develop and update action plans for external communications are a joint responsibility of WP8 and WP7 leads. The external communication plan will be reviewed and approved by members of the PMC.

Annex 5: Journals and venues for dissemination of SIENNA outputs and results

Below is a list of journals, covering some audiences outlined for SIENNA scientific dissemination in the technology fields of SIENNA, ethics, law, policy and innovation studies, extending to members of civil society and public and private sectors.

The lists in this annex will be updated and maintained by Trilateral Research based on the needs of the project and in discussion with consortium partners.

Journal	Publisher	Readership	Impact factor & publication frequency
Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research	Routledge	Readers interested in European developments that contribute to the improvement of social science knowledge and to the setting of a policy-focused European research agenda	Impact factor (2014): 0.400 Publication Frequency: 4 issues per year
Journal of Information, Communications and Ethics in Society	Emerald	Academics from anthropology, business, computer science, information systems, law, library and information sciences, media, philosophy, politics, psychology, sociology; professional practitioners; government officials; policy makers	Impact factor: Not available Publication frequency: 4 issues a year
International Review of Law, Computers and Technology	Routledge	Information technologies researchers, academics	Impact factor: Not available Publication Frequency: 3 issues per year
Journal of Responsible Innovation	Taylor & Francis	Humanists, social scientists, policy analysts and legal scholars, and natural scientists and engineers	Impact factor: Not available Publication Frequency: 3 issues per year
Human–Computer Interaction	Taylor & Francis	Professionals interested in the scientific implications and practical relevance of how computer systems should be designed and used.	Impact Factor (2014): 3.143 Publication Frequency: 6 issues per year
Ethics and Information Technology	Springer	Readers interested in technology assessment, cultural studies, public policy analysis, cognitive science, social and anthropological studies in technology, mass-communication, and legal studies	Impact factor (2014): 1.021 Publication frequency: 4 issues a year

Journal	Publisher	Readership	Impact factor & publication frequency
IEEE Technology and Society Magazine	IEEE Society on Social Implications of Technology	Engineering and IT professionals	Impact factor: 0.556 Publication frequency: 4 per year
Horizon: The EU Research and Innovation Magazine (open access)	European Commission	EU researchers, policymakers	Impact factor: not available Publication frequency: Ongoing
Frontiers in Robotics and AI	Frontiers Media S.A	Academic researchers	Publication frequency: Ongoing
Science and Engineering Ethics	Springer	Readers interested in ethical issues of direct concern to scientists and engineers. Topics cover professional education, standards and ethics in research and practice, extending to the effects of innovation on society at large	Impact factor: 0,963 Publication Frequency: 1 volume with 6 issues per year

Table 21: Tentative list of journals for SIENNA scientific dissemination

Potential third-party venues for scientific dissemination and communication

The consortium partners have identified the following external events at which they intend to disseminate the project's results and outputs (this list will be finalised based on the timings of the events and availability of the project's results).

Event	Organiser	Audience
ETHICOMP conference	De Montfort University	Various communities involved in the development, implementation, use of computing and reflection on it in its various guises
Computers, Privacy and Data Protection Conference	Vrije Universiteit Brussel, the Université de Namur and Tilburg University.	Academia, public and private sectors and civil society from over 40 different countries
The EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF)	EuroScience	Thinkers, innovators, policy makers, journalists and educators from over 90 countries to discuss current and future breakthroughs in contemporary science
International Conference on Human- Computer Interaction	HCI International	Those interested in scientific information on theoretical, generic and applied areas of HCI.
International Association	International Association of	Those working in bioethics and

Event	Organiser	Audience
of Bioethics World Congress	Bioethics	related fields, facilitating mutual contact, and encouraging the discussion of cross-cultural aspects in bioethics
European Association of Health Law bi-annual conference/events	European Association of Health Law	EU and international lawyers involved in health law issues and collaborating on issues of importance in the development of health law and related policies
Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA) conference	University of Texas at Arlington (Professor Fillia Makedon)	Researchers working in healthcare and assisted living
Annual Conference on Governance of Emerging Technologies: Law, Policy, and Ethics	Variable	Academics from diverse fields interested in the governance issues and challenges posed by emerging technologies. Discussions with stakeholders on regulatory, governance, legal, policy, social and ethical aspects of emerging technologies
Annual Conference of the Society for Neuroscience and International Neuroethics Society (have joint events)	Society for Neuroscience and International Neuroethics Society	World's largest organization of scientists and physicians devoted to understanding the brain and nervous system. The most important neuroscience conference
World Congress on Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine	Tissue Engineering & Regenerative Medicine International Society	International community of researchers engaged in the field of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine; promotes the informed discussion of challenges and therapeutic benefits of the application of the technologies
Augmented Human International Conference	Variable	Researchers from many disciplines and stakeholders interested in augmentation with smart material, brain augmentation, augmented reality applications, ethics of augmented human technologies
RightsCon	Access Now	human rights experts, business leaders, technologists, engineers, investors, activists,

Event	Organiser	Audience
		and government representatives
We Robot: Conference on legal and policy issues related to robotics	University of Miami School of Law	Academics and practitioners, engineers, social scientists, legal scholars
Annual European Data Protection and Privacy Conference	Forum Europe	Cross-sector delegates, policymakers, stakeholders
Digital ethics summit (UK, 13 December 2017)	TechUK in partnership with the Royal Statistical Society, Wellcome Trust, Royal Society, British Academy, University of Oxford Data Ethics Lab, Open Data Institute, The Alan Turing Institute and the Leverhulme Centre for the Future of Intelligence and sponsored by Microsoft, The Nuffield Foundation and Yoti.	Philosophers, academics, industry and policy makers to consider the digital and data ethics question.

Table 22: Tentative list of third party venues for scientific dissemination and communication

Annex 6: Guidelines for SIENNA disseminations and communications review

This document outlines of the IP review processes for publication of results, guidelines for SIENNA communications and routines in case of negative publicity. The content of this document was established by PMC decision on October 18, 2018.

Note: These guidelines **only** apply to dissemination of results **from the SIENNA project** and communication **about the project or its results**. You have no obligation to inform about dissemination that is not related to SIENNA. This also does not apply to SIENNA deliverables which have their own review process.

Disseminating results

RESULTS DISSEMINATION Review Guidelines	
Scientific publications	
Before starting the writing process,	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lead authors should be sure that the work they are developing is their own and/or that they have contacted all those contributors who have done the bulk of the work 2. Lead authors need to check with main WP leaders/coordinators if they want to write an article using data generated from the project (or any article? i.e. editorial?) 3. Lead authors and contributors together should decide on authorship, based on the following criteria: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work; AND 2. Drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content; AND 3. Final approval of the version to be published; AND 4. Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved. 	
Should authors not fulfil all these criteria by the end of the article, authorship may be revoked	
30* days before submission to a journal	<p>Partners: Right to review the manuscript for IP infringements. Right to object within 30 days</p> <p>According to section 8.4.2.3 of the Consortium Agreement, an objection is justified if</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected (b) The objecting Party's legitimate interests in relation to the Results or Background would be significantly harmed <p>Communication team: Check of acknowledgement and disclaimers, plans communication of published results</p> <p>Lead authors: Decide whether any recommendations made by partners during the</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lead author must ensure they have contacted and made aware anyone who has contributed to the work and/or who will be an author on the work. 2. Include the following acknowledgement: This article has been adapted from/is based upon the XXXXX report/findings/results of the SIENNA project (Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact) - which has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716. 3. Include disclaimer: This article and its contents reflect only the views of the authors and does not intend to 	

<p>reflect those of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Send manuscript to: crb-sienna-review@lists.uu.se 5. If your publication is in another language, please provide a short summary in English. 6. If no objections within 30 days, submit to journal. 7. Keep the final version of your paper (after journal review, before journal layout, in preparation for step 8) 8. When the paper is accepted, and again when published (online first), tell the Uppsala communications team (josepine.fernnow@crb.uu.se & anna.holm@crb.uu.se) for tracking and to ensure your publication is communicated through SIENNA channels. 9. Post-publication, send link to journal and an 'author version' of your paper (last version before journal layout) to anna.holm@crb.uu.se for green open access (parallel publishing) in the UU DiVA repository. <p><i>*According to the Consortium Agreement, Partners need to send their manuscript to all parties 45 days before publication, who have the right to object within 30 days. To make this manageable, the PMC agreed to 30 days before submission at their meeting on October 18, 2018.</i></p>	<p>IP review process are to be included. If included, please acknowledge this contribution.</p>
<p>Abstracts</p>	
<p>Make sure to</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tell the communications team about your plans to submit using the online tracking form: http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/dissemination/ 2. If possible, include the SIENNA acknowledgement (or an abbreviated version of it): The SIENNA project - <i>Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact</i> - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716. 3. Once submitted, send the abstract to the communications team for tracking and reporting purposes (anna.holm@crb.uu.se). 4. After acceptance and presentation, update the communications team by submitting the online tracking form again! http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/dissemination/ 	<p>Communication team: Tracks and plans communications about your presentation (should it be accepted)</p>
<p>Presentations (Posters and PowerPoints)</p>	

<p>Make sure to</p>	<p>Communication team: Check of acknowledgement and disclaimers</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tell the communications team about your plans and ask for layout help 2. Include acknowledgement: The SIENNA project - <i>Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact</i> - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716. 3. Include disclaimer: This presentation/poster/other and its contents reflects only SIENNA's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. 4. Update the communications team by filling out the online tracking form http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/dissemination/. 	<p>Design support for posters</p> <p>Tracking & reporting</p>

Communicating about SIENNA and published results

<p>COMMUNICATION guidelines</p>	
<p>Opinion editorials:</p>	
<p>At the planning stage</p>	<p>PMC: Can help decide whether this should be an official SIENNA opinion text, or only the authors'.</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inform the PMC and communications team about your plans and to discuss how to fit SIENNA messages in your text. 	<p>Communications team: Can help draft and edit text to fit with SIENNA key messages.</p>
<p>One week before submission</p>	<p>Checks acknowledgement and disclaimer</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Include acknowledgement: The SIENNA project - <i>Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact</i> - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716. 3. Include disclaimer: This article and its contents reflects only SIENNA's view (alternatively, depending on what is agreed: the view of the authors and not the view of the SIENNA project). The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. 4. If this is an official SIENNA text, partners should be given an opportunity to see the text before publication. If this is the author's text only, you still need to send your text to the communications team (josepine.fernou@crb.uu.se & anna.holm@crb.uu.se) for tracking and planning communications. 	

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Keep the final version of your paper (after journal review, before journal layout, in preparation for step 7) 6. When the editorial is accepted, and again when published (online first), tell the Uppsala communications team (josepine.fernou@crb.uu.se & anna.holm@crb.uu.se) for tracking and to ensure your publication is communicated through SIENNA channels 7. Post-publication, send link to journal and an 'author version' of your paper (last version before journal layout) to anna.holm@crb.uu.se for green open access (parallel publishing) in the UU DiVA repository. 	
<p>In your own channels:</p>	
<p>Make sure to</p>	<p>Communications team: Thanks you and reminds you to make sure you do not forget the acknowledgement and disclaimer next time.</p> <p>Offers advice on channels and multipliers if you ask.</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Include acknowledgement: The SIENNA project - <i>Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact</i> - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716. 2. Include disclaimer: This presentation/poster/other and its contents reflects only SIENNA's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. 3. Inform the communications team by filling out the online tracking form http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/dissemination/. 4. Send your newsletter article, web-news text, PowerPoint. Social media or web link to anna.holm@crb.uu.se for tracking. 	
<p>In third-party channels (for example newsletter from an organisation who is not partner in SIENNA)</p>	
<p>Before communication (ideally 5 working days)</p>	<p>Communications team: Can help draft and edit text to fit with SIENNA key messages.</p> <p>Checks acknowledgement and disclaimer</p> <p>Tracks and multiplies messages in SIENNA official channels.</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inform the communications team by filling out the online tracking form http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/dissemination/. 2. Send your newsletter- or web-news text, PowerPoint or other to the Uppsala University communications team (josepine.fernou@crb.uu.se and anna.holm@crb.uu.se) 	
<p>In social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter etc)</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thank you for sharing! Let the communications team know you shared information about SIENNA (twitter @SiennaEthics) and we can multiply it in our channels 	<p>Communications team: Tracks and thanks you!</p>

In the media: Interviews, press-releases, reporting about SIENNA in international or local media

1. Inform the communications team beforehand by filling out the online tracking form <http://www.sienna-project.eu/contact/dissemination/>.
2. Send published text, or link to video or radio to the Uppsala University communications team (josepine.fernnow@crb.uu.se and anna.holm@crb.uu.se)

Communications team: Tracks and multiplies your message.

Routines in case of negative press

In case of negative press: If you receive bad press (e.g. your opinions are misrepresented in an interview, you are accused of a criminal act, slandered or criticised) or receive public criticism in a meeting (either related to SIENNA, or other professional or personal activities that could potentially damage the SIENNA “brand” or your personal reputation) tell us immediately so that we can plan how to mitigate any risks this could create for the project and yourself.

1. Make sure you inform both the SIENNA project and your own organisation:
 - a. Inform your PI, the head of your department, your organisations press office
 - b. The SIENNA Coordinator: p.a.e.brey@utwente.nl **who will ensure the EC project officer and policy officer are informed.**
 - c. SIENNA Deputy Coordinator: rowena.rodriques@trilateralresearch.com
 - d. SIENNA Communications lead: josepine.fernnow@crb.uu.se

Communications team: Tracks and assists you if necessary

Coordinator: Informs EC project officer and policy officer

Coordinator and Deputy Coordinator: Assists you and liaises with your organisation and communications team to mitigate risks to the project and individual.

Your own organisation: Implements own routines to mitigate risks for own organisation and the individual, supported by SIENNA if required

Annex 7: Process for evaluating SIENNA influence and impact

A process for tracking communications, together with Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) for communications and processes for evaluating SIENNA influence and impact will be developed in 2018. The process will be described in a document circulated to the consortium, and included as an annex to this plan.

Annex 8: Risks and risk mitigation

Risk relating to SIENNA communications	Level	Mitigation
UU ceases development of the InfoGlue platform (Content Management System for web).	Medium	Uppsala University will procure and develop a new content management system (CMS) for web. The process starts in 2018. This means further development of the InfoGlue platform where the SIENNA project website is currently hosted will cease. This means no new functionality will be added to the website. Should this be a problem for SIENNA, it will be possible to migrate the content to the new UU CMS (which will be likely be available in 2020). Support for the existing website will remain.
Key personnel leave the project.	Low	The SIENNA communications team consists of two people at Uppsala University, allowing knowledge transfer.
Failure to drive and attract traffic to the SIENNA website.	Medium	The SIENNA website has a generic URL. This requires taking SEO measures when developing content for the website (i.e., using keywords in headings, synonyms in text, adapting text to reach low readability scores etcetera). Mitigating this risk also requires using other media to drive traffic to the website. The communications team will develop a plan for this.
GDPR requirements for privacy notices and opt-in procedures could hinder recruitment of newsletter subscribers and use of stakeholder contact list developed by WP1.	High	Strategy to mitigate this risk will be developed by WP1, WP8 and WP7 together.
Procedures for review and approval could impede communications coming out of the project.	Low	Clear guidelines for review and approval will be developed by WP7.
Failure to communicate the complexity of ethical and legal dilemmas relating to technology that is difficult to understand.	Medium	WP7 will develop anchoring strategies and framing for each technology area to support public understanding of science.
Risk that SIENNA communications become too academic to be understood by all stakeholder audiences.	Medium	WP7 will provide editorial support and review for external communications to support adaptation of messages to audience and channel

Risk of negative publicity.	Low	WP7 will provide media training for SIENNA consortium members and develop routines for handling negative publicity.
Risk that lack of competence (e.g. journalistic experience) within the communications team impedes SIENNA communications.	Low	The SIENNA communications team includes an officer with over 15 years' experience communicating ethical, legal and social issues relating to human genetics and genomics and other research, writing for different media (including press releases) and leading communications in international projects. WP7 will liaise with press officers in partner organisations to support press communications to mitigate this risk and benefit SIENNA by adding local knowledge and networks.
Risk that diversity in networks, languages and expertise, regions and countries make messages coming out of SIENNA irrelevant to national and regional and/or international audiences	Low	SIENNA partners will take an active role in adapting, translating and communicating messages to their networks. WP7 will liaise with WP6 to ensure that the level of generalisability is clearly communicated towards the end of the project.
Risk that public deliverable reports impedes scientific publication as results are already published in the public domain	High	The PMC will discuss publication plans in relation to timing of online publication of deliverable reports to ensure publication of deliverables do not interfere with plans for scholarly publication.

Table 23: Risks and risk mitigation

Annex 9: Communication achievements

Press releases, news and media coverage of the SIENNA project are tracked and made publically available in the news section of the SIENNA website, along with feeds from SIENNA social media (<http://www.sienna-project.eu/news/>).

Date	Type	Location	By-line	Title/link	Language	Sentiment
2017-04-28	Press-release from the University of Twente (in relation to signing of the Grant Agreement) with quotes from Philip Brey	University of Twente, the Netherlands	Laurens van der Velde	Onderzoek naar ethische en juridische aspecten van nieuwe technologie	Dutch	Positive
	Translated version of global release	University of Twente, the Netherlands		Research on ethical and legal aspects of new technologies	English	Positive
	Translated version of global release	SIENNA website		European funding for research on ethical and legal aspects of new technologies	English	Positive
2017-05-02	Interview with Philip Brey	NPO Radio 1, the Netherlands	Lara Rense	Groot Europees onderzoek naar regels voor nieuwe technologieën	Dutch	Positive
2017-05-05	Interview with Philip Brey	Computable, the Netherlands	Rik Sanders	UT buigt zich over ethiek en technologie	Dutch	Positive
2017-05-13	Interview with Philip Brey	Tubantia, the Netherlands	Laurien van Ulzen	Dit zijn de 3 ethische grenzen aan technologie, vindt UT-professor	Dutch	Positive
2017-05-22	Listing of SIENNA among research consortia (RI enterprises)	Netherlands Research Integrity Network website, the Netherlands	N/A	Stakeholder-Informed Ethics for New Technologies with High Socio-Economic and Human Rights Impact (SIENNA)	English	Positive
2017-10-19	Global press-release from the University of Twente with quotes from Rowena Rodrigues and Philip Brey	University of Twente (through EurekAlert)	Laurens van der Velde	Preparing the ground for responsible innovation: International research team to assess ethical and human right impact of new technologies	Dutch	Positive
	Web news mirroring global release	SIENNA web	Laurens van der Velde	SIENNA: Preparing the ground for responsible innovation	English	Positive

Date	Type	Location	By-line	Title/link	Language	Sentiment
	Web news mirroring content from global release from the Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB) with quote from Heidi Howard focusing on contribution from Uppsala University	Uppsala University, Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics, Sweden	Josepine Fernow		English	Positive
	Translated version of web news	Uppsala University, Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics, Sweden	Josepine Fernow	SIENNA-projektet lägger grunden för ansvarsfull teknikanvändning	Swedish	Positive
	Web news from Trilateral Research mirroring content from global release, focusing on Trilateral contribution to the project	Trilateral Research Ltd, United Kingdom	N/A	Trilateral to support the co-ordination of multi-million Euro project on ethics and human rights impact of new technologies	English	Positive
2017-10-24	Release of Dutch language version of global press release	University of Twente, the Netherlands	Laurens van der Velde	Ethische basis voor verantwoorde innovatie	Dutch	Positive
	Reprint of Dutch version of press release	link Magazine	N/A	Ethische basis voor verantwoorde innovatie,	Dutch	Positive
2017-10-26	Press release from the University of Granada, mirroring part of content from global release, with quote from Javier Valls Prieto	UGR divulga, Canal UGR, Univeristy of Granada, Spain	Javier Valls Prieto	Un equipo de investigación internacional evaluará el impacto de las nuevas tecnologías en los derechos humanos,	Spanish	Positive
	News mirroring content from University of Granada press release, with quote from Javier Valls Prieto	20 minutos, Spain	N/A	Investigadores evaluarán el impacto de las nuevas tecnologías en los derechos humanos,	Spanish	Positive
2017-10-30	Web news with content from global press release	Dalian University of Technology	N/A	我校人文学部科技伦理团队参加欧盟科技伦理合作项目启动会议,	Mandarin	Assumed positive

Date	Type	Location	By-line	Title/link	Language	Sentiment
2017-10-31	Blog post about SIENNA mirroring part of content from global press release	Ethics Blog, Uppsala University, Sweden	Josepine Fernow	Ethics, human rights and responsible innovation	English	Positive
	Translated blog post	Etikbloggen, Uppsala University, Sweden	Josepine Fernow	Teknik, etik och mänskliga rättigheter	Swedish	Positive
2017-11-03	News article reporting from Brave New World Conference, Netherlands, including quotes from Philip Brey and mention of the SIENNA project	DutchNews.nl, the Netherlands	Max Opray	Cyborgs urge humans to see the light at Leiden's Brave New World conference	English	Positive
2017-11-21	Web news mirroring part of global release	Program for Bioethics, Applied Ethics and Public Health, UFRJ, Brazil	Maria Clara Dias, Marcelo de Araujo	UFRJ recebeu 38 mil euros para participação em projeto da União Europeia	Portugese	Positive

Table 24: Communication achievements

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